

GENETIC STUDIES IN *DESI* COTTON (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)

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Abstract

Cotton (Gossypium hirsutum L.) belongs to Malvaceae family which is an often-cross-pollinated crop. The present investigation was carried out using thirty hybrids for quantitative and qualitative traits of cotton to estimate the genetic variability present within genotypes. The material was evaluated in randomized block design with four replications during kharif, 2023 at Cotton Research Station, MB, Farm, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. The differences between genotypes were significant for all the characters, which revealed considerable amount of variability for all the traits under study. The high genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation was observed for number of bolls per plant followed by number of monopodia per plant, boll weight, number of bolls per plant, micronaire value and seed cotton yield per plant suggesting the presence of considerable amount of genetic variability. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as per cent of mean were observed for number of sympodia per plant, boll weight, number of bolls per plant, plant height, micronaire value and seed cotton yield per plant indicates the role of additive genes and less environmental influence on the characters and presence of adequate heritable variation. Thus it can be concluded that selection based on the traits like number of sympodia per plant, boll weight and number of bolls per plant would be beneficial for further crop improvement.

Keywords: Cotton, genotypes, variability, heritability, genetic advance

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.) is an important economical crop grown for fibre crop of the world. It is also an important source of edible oil, protein and cottonseed meal for animals. Cotton belongs to Malvaceae family and genus *Gossypium*, which consists of five allotetraploid and forty-five diploid species among them only four species are cultivated worldwide (Ulloa *et al.*, 2006). India has the distinction of growing all the four spinnable lint bearing species of *Gossypium viz.*, *G. hirsutum*, *G. barbadense*, *G. arboreum* and *G. herbaceum*. Among these four cultivated species, *Desi* cotton (*G. arboreum* L.) is known for its resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses production potential, as demonstrated by the release of number of stable varieties and hybrids. Cotton breeders have continued their efforts to exploit the cotton germplasm to develop high yielding cotton varieties with acceptable fibre quality. Peohman and Selper (1995) clarified that the yield contributing, and fibre quality traits are heritable in nature. Thus, quantitative and qualitative traits can be improved by utilizing appropriate breeding programme by developing new cross combinations. For this purpose, breeders are interested to have sufficient knowledge of genetic components such as genetic variability, coefficient of variation, heritability and genetic advance to devise the breeding technique in accordance to their breeding objectives (Dhamayanathi *et al.*, 2010; Ali and Khan, 2007). Selection is basic tool in crop breeding programme. Presence of genetic variability among the genotypes is basic need for practicing selection for improvement in seed cotton yield. Plant breeders always encouraged the genetic variability in breeding populations and considered it as the initial requirement to screen the genetic material for different biotic and abiotic stresses. This genetic variability is further exploited by utilizing different statistical tools. Heritability is an effective statistical tool that helps the plant breeder to estimate the environmental influence for various traits in breeding nursery. It is also an effective index to determine the extent of trait that is transferred from parents to offsprings. Thus, heritability when coupled with genetics advance and genetic variability could be powerful tool for plant researcher to select proper breeding program (Chandio *et al.*, 2003; Baloch, 2004). Therefore the present study was conducted to evaluate the genetic variability and heritability for numerous yield and yield attributing characters in a set of genotypes. Such information could be beneficial in formulating effective selection method for development of new

genotypes with enhanced yield and its contributing traits.

Materials and Methods

This experiment was conducted at Cotton Research Station, MB, Farm, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. during Kharif, 2023-24. The experimental plant materials for the present study comprised of thirty hybrids of cotton (*G. hirsutum* L.), which were procured at Cotton Research Station, MB Farm, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani (Table 1). These hybrids were sown in rows of 6 m length with spacing of 60 cm between rows and 30 cm between plants in randomized block design with two replications. All the recommended package of practices were followed to raise healthy crop. In each replication five competitive plants were randomly selected and observations were recorded on twelve characters. Observations on fibre quality traits in each replication were recorded by High Volume Instrument (HVI) in ICC mode at CIRCOT, Nagpur. Analysis of variance of the observations recorded on different characters was carried out as per the standard procedure suggested by Fisher (1925). According to Burton and Devane (1953), genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation were estimated based on the estimates of genotypic and phenotypic variances. The genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation were categorized as per the method suggested by Shiva Subramanian and Menon (1973) i.e. 0-10% = Low, 10-20% = Moderate, Above 20% = High. Heritability in broad sense was calculated as the ratio of genotypic variance to the phenotypic variance and expressed as percentage. The calculated heritability was classified into three groups as suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955) i.e. 0-30% = Low, 30-60% = Moderate, 60% = High. Genetic advance was calculated as per the formula given by Johnson *et al.* (1955), and also categorized as 0-10% = Low, 10-20% = Moderate, Above 20% = High. The data recorded on the traits were analysed by INDOSTAT software.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of variance for the sixteen seed cotton yield and its attributing traits revealed that the mean sum of squares due to genotypes were highly significant for all the traits studied. Therefore, adequate variability was present for yield and yield contributing traits in the material studied (Table 2). Possibility of improving economic characters through selection in crop depends largely on the extent of genetic variability present in the population. Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation gives the

idea about the extent of variability present in genetic population, whereas heritability is useful in predicting the role of transmission factors in phenotypes expression and ultimately selection of elite genotypes from the segregating population. Heritability along with genetic advance favours the fixation of genetic factors for any particular trait. The outcomes related to general mean, range and genetic parameters of variation, broad sense heritability (h^2) and genetic advance as per cent mean for all the characters presented in Table 3. The estimates of Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were observed high for boll weight (18.93% and 19.45%), number of sympodia per plant (19.01% and 22.42%), number of bolls per plant (15.39% and 15.94%) and Seed cotton yield per plant (17.94% and 18.05%), which is due to presence of huge amount of variability amongst all the genotypes studied for the traits. Similarity between both the values depicts the least influence of environment on these characters emphasizing a greater scope of improvement through selection. The results are in concordance with the findings of Erande *et al.* (2014), Aarthi *et al.* (2018), Pandiyan *et al.* (2019), Praveen *et al.* (2019) and Siva Reddy *et al.* (2019). The measured values of Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for plant height (9.45% and 9.82%), fibre strength (9.52% and 9.80%) and micronaire (10.68% and 10.89%) were moderate which suggest the presence of moderate amount of variability which can be utilized through selection for efficient breeding programme. The results are in accordance with the findings of Dhivya *et al.* (2014), Aarthi *et al.* (2018), Pandiyan *et al.* (2019) and Shruti *et al.* (2019). The Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation measured for the traits like days to flowering (4.66% and 4.78%), days to maturity (3.69% and 3.77%), Uniformity ratio (4.71% and 4.75%), upper half mean length (6.91% and 7.12%) and ginning out turn (5.90% and 7.28%) were low indicating that there is less variability among the genotypes studied. Similar results were also observed by Vinodhana *et al.* (2013), Erande *et al.* (2014), Aarthi *et al.* (2018), Pandiyan *et al.* (2019), Shruti *et al.* (2019), and Siva Reddy *et al.* (2019). Whereas low genotypic coefficient of variation (3.69%) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (3.77%) recorded for days to maturity. Which indicates that there is influence of environment. Similar kind of result was reported by Vinodhana *et al.* (2013).

The higher estimates of heritability were recorded for days to 50% flowering (95.28%), days to maturity (96.12%), boll weight (94.44%), number of bolls per plant (93.19%), plant height (92.48%), Uniformity ratio (98.70%), fibre strength (94.48%), upper half mean length (94.18%), micronaire value (96.25%) and seed cotton yield per plant (98.77%). These findings are in agreement with the earlier findings of Erande *et al.* (2014), Eswari *et al.* (2017), Aarthi *et al.* (2018), Deshmukh *et al.* (2019), Manonmani *et al.* (2019), Pandiyan *et al.* (2019), Praveen *et al.* (2019), Shruti *et al.* (2019) and Siva Reddy *et al.* (2019). This suggested the greater effectiveness of selection and improvement to be expected for these characters in future breeding programmes as the genetic variance is mostly due to the additive gene action. Moderate heritability was observed for number of sympodia per plant (71.89%) and ginning out turn (65.68%). Similar kinds of results were reported by Dhivya *et al.* (2014), Erande *et al.* (2014) and Monisha *et al.* (2018). Heritability approximations along with genetic advance would be more worthwhile in expecting improvement of seed cotton yield under phenotypic selection than heritability estimates alone as suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955). If heritability is mainly due to non-additive gene effect, the expected genetic advance would be low, and if there is additive gene effect, a high genetic advance may be expected (Panse, 1957). In this study, high heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percentage of mean was observed for boll weight (37.91%), Number of sympodia per plant (33.19%), number of bolls per plant (30.61%) and seed cotton yield per plant (36.74%). It indicates that most likely the

heritability is due to additive gene effects and selection could be beneficial by utilizing the fixable genes for improvement. Similar results were also reported by Aarthi *et al.* (2018), Monisha *et al.* (2018), Pandiyan *et al.* (2019) and Praveen *et al.* (2019).

High heritability coupled with moderate genetic advance as percentage of mean was observed for plant height (18.72%), fibre strength (19.07%), upper half mean length (13.82%) and micronaire value (21.58%). Similar results were found by Monisha *et al.* (2018), and Moderate heritability accompanied with moderate magnitude of genetic advance as per cent of mean was observed for ginning out turn (9.55%). These results are in agreement with the findings of Dhivya *et al.* (2014) and Praveen *et al.* (2019). The obtained results indicate the operation of both additive and non-additive gene action and desired results may not be obtained by simple selection. High heritability coupled with low genetic advance as per cent of mean recorded for days to 50% flowering (9.38%) and days to maturity (7.46%) which indicates the presence of non-additive gene action which offers a limited scope of improvement. The high heritability is being exhibited due to favourable influence of environment rather than genotype indicating the possibility of improvement in these traits through heterosis breeding rather than simple selection. Similar results were reported by Erande *et al.* (2014), Eswari *et al.* (2017) and Manonmani *et al.* (2019). The heritability is being unveiled due to favourable influence of environment rather than genotype indicating the possibility of improvement of this trait through heterosis breeding, rather than simple selection. Similar findings were observed by Erande *et al.* (2014), Monisha *et al.* (2018) and Praveen *et al.* (2019).

Conclusion

The genotypic coefficients of variation for all the characters studied were lesser than the phenotypic coefficients of variation indicating the effect of environment. The range of GCV and PCV were recorded higher for number of monopodia per plant followed by number of bolls per plant, lint yield per plant and seed cotton yield per plant indicating the influence of measurable amount of variability. Whereas, low GCV and PCV were resulted by days to flowering followed by days to boll bursting, ginning per cent, seed index, oil content, 2.5% span length, Micronaire and fibre strength. Thus, suggesting the selection in desirable manner would play a better role in crop improvement. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as per cent of mean were observed for plant height, number of monopodia per plant, number of sympodia per plant and number of bolls per plant. High heritability coupled with moderate genetic advance recorded for boll weight and fibre strength. The traits which exhibit high heritability coupled with high genetic advance indicating the role of additive genes and selection based on these traits like plant height, number of monopodia per plant, number of sympodia per plant and number of bolls per plant would be beneficial for further crop improvement.

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Fig 1: Graphical representation of genetic parameters for sixteen characters in *Desi* cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)

Table 1: List of hybrids

Sr. No.	Hybrids	Sr. No.	Hybrids	Sr. No.	Hybrids	Sr. No.	Hybrids	Sr. No.	Hybrids
1.	PA 785 x PA 810	7.	PA 873 x PA 08	13.	PA 833 x AKA 8	19.	PA 904 x PA 402	25.	PA 809 x JLA 505
2.	PA 785 x PA 08	8.	PA 873 x AKA 8	14.	PA 833 x PA 402	20.	PA 904 x JLA 505	26.	CNA 1032 x PA 810
3.	PA 785 x AKA 8	9.	PA 873 x PA 402	15.	PA 833 x JLA 505	21.	PA 809 x PA 810	27.	CNA 1032 x PA 08
4.	PA 785 x PA 402	10.	PA 873 x JLA 505	16.	PA 904 x PA 810	22.	PA 809 x PA 08	28.	CNA 1032 x AKA 8
5.	PA 785 x JLA 505	11.	PA 833 x PA 810	17.	PA 904 x PA 08	23.	PA 809 x AKA 8	29.	CNA 1032 x PA 402
6.	PA 873 x PA 810	12.	PA 833 x PA 08	18.	PA 904 x AKA 8	24.	PA 809 x PA 402	30.	CNA 1032 x JLA 505

Table 2: Mean sum of squares values for yield contributing and fibre quality characters in cotton

Source of variation	d. f.	Mean sum of squares											
		Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Boll weight (g)	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Plant height (cm)	Uniformity ratio	Fibre strength	UHML (mm)	Micronaire value (µg/inch)	Ginning outturn	Seed cotton Yield per plant (g)
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Replications	1	0.81	1.66	0.02	6.01	0.15	8.82	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.39	0.006
Treatments	29	28.10**	38.95**	0.53**	30.03**	15.02**	292.63**	28.85**	13.87**	7.79**	0.58**	10.36**	100.10**
Error	29	0.67	0.77	0.01	4.91	0.53	11.44	0.19	0.39	0.23	0.01	2.14	0.62

Table 3: Genetic parameters of variation for seed cotton yield and its contributing traits in cotton

Sr. No.	Character	Mean	Range		Coefficient of Variation		h ² bs (%)	GA	GAM (%)
			Min	Max	GCV (%)	PCV (%)			
1	Days to 50 % flowering	51.65	47.00	58.00	4.66	4.78	95.28	7.44	9.38
2	Days to maturity	118.20	112.0	128.5	3.69	3.77	96.12	8.82	7.46
3	Boll weight (g)	2.68	1.50	3.37	18.93	19.48	94.44	1.01	37.91
4	Number of sympodia per plant	18.65	12.50	26.50	19.01	22.42	71.89	6.19	33.19
5	Number of bolls per plant	17.48	12.50	27.00	15.39	15.94	93.19	5.35	30.61
6	Plant height (cm)	125.45	114.00	141.00	9.45	9.82	92.48	23.48	18.72
7	Uniformity ratio	80.21	80.65	84.10	4.72	4.75	98.70	7.74	9.65
8	Fibre strength	27.26	27.15	29.55	9.52	9.80	94.48	5.19	19.07
9	UHML (mm)	28.13	28.30	29.80	6.91	7.12	94.18	3.89	13.82
10	Micronaire value (µg/inch)	5.01	3.70	5.75	10.68	10.89	96.25	1.08	21.58
11	Ginning out turn (%)	34.35	31.36	36.65	5.90	7.28	65.68	3.38	9.85
12	Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	39.30	17.40	29.60	17.94	18.05	98.77	14.44	36.74